

PROOF OF KNUTH'S BINOMIAL IDENTITY (5.43)

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ABSTRACT. In this manuscript we prove a remarkable Binomial identity (5.43) given by Donald Knuth in his fundamental work entitled Concrete Mathematics.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this manuscript we prove a remarkable Binomial identity (5.43) given by Donald Knuth in his fundamental work entitled Concrete Mathematics, see [1, p. 190]

Proposition 1.1 (Knuth's Binomial identity (5.43)). *For non-negative integers n , and for arbitrary integers s, r*

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{r-sk}{n} (-1)^k = s^n$$

2. PROOF OF KNUTH'S BINOMIAL IDENTITY

We begin our proof by recalling the formula for n -order finite differences of function f

$$\Delta^n f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{n-k} f(x+k)$$

Now, we define the binomial function F , such that

$$F(x) = \binom{r-sx}{n}$$

Thus, the t -order forward finite difference of F is

$$\Delta^t F(x) = \sum_{k=0}^t \binom{t}{k} \binom{r-s(x+k)}{n} (-1)^{t-k}$$

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We may notice that the equation above quite reminds the structure of Knuth's binomial identity (1.1). By evaluating $\Delta^t F(x)$ in zero, we reach our goal even further, because

$$\Delta^t F(0) = \sum_{k=0}^t \binom{t}{k} \binom{r-sk}{n} (-1)^{t-k}$$

Next, by setting $t = n$ gives the exact structure of (1.1), such that

$$\Delta^n F(0) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{r-sk}{n} (-1)^{n-k}$$

Still, it may not be immediately clear why $\Delta^n F(0) = (-1)^n s^n$, as the Proposition (1.1) states. To make the things up, we refer to the formula (5.42) in Concrete mathematics, see [1, p. 190],

$$(-1)^n \Delta^n F(0) = \sum_k \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k [a_0 + a_1 k^1 + a_2 k^2 + \dots + a_n k^n] = (-1)^n n! a_n,$$

which states that n -th difference of a polynomial of degree n in k equals to the coefficient of k^n multiplied by $(-1)^n n!$. This helps us a lot, because the binomial coefficient $\binom{r-sk}{n}$ is actually a polynomial of degree n in $(r-sk)$. The famous identity in unsigned Stirling numbers of the first kind $\left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right]$ shows it clearly

$$\binom{n}{k} = \sum_{j=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{k-j}}{k!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} k \\ j \end{smallmatrix} \right] n^j$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{r-sk}{n} &= \frac{(-1)^{n-0}}{n!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ 0 \end{smallmatrix} \right] (r-sk)^0 + \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ 1 \end{smallmatrix} \right] (r-sk)^1 + \dots + \frac{(-1)^{n-n}}{n!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ n \end{smallmatrix} \right] (r-sk)^n \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-j}}{n!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ j \end{smallmatrix} \right] (r-sk)^j \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the coefficient a_n of k^n is

$$a_n = [k^n] \frac{1}{n!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ n \end{smallmatrix} \right] (r-sk)^n = \frac{1}{n!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ n \end{smallmatrix} \right] [k^n] (r-sk)^n$$

By Binomial theorem,

$$(r-sk)^n = \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} r^{n-j} (-1)^j (sk)^j$$

Thus, by extracting the coefficient of k^n , we isolate the term for $j = n$, such that

$$[k^n](r - sk)^n = \binom{n}{n} r^0 (-1)^n s^n = (-1)^n s^n$$

Hence, the coefficient a_n of k^n equals to

$$a_n = \frac{1}{n!} \begin{bmatrix} n \\ n \end{bmatrix} (-1)^n s^n = (-1)^n \frac{s^n}{n!}$$

Which implies that,

$$\Delta^n F(0) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{r - sk}{n} (-1)^{n-k} = n! a_n = (-1)^n n! \frac{s^n}{n!} = (-1)^n s^n$$

Therefore, the Knuth's identity (1.1) is indeed true

$$(-1)^n \Delta^n F(0) = (-1)^{2n} n! \frac{s^n}{n!} = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{r - sk}{n} (-1)^k = s^n$$

This completes the proof of Proposition (1.1). □

It is quite remarkable that although the identity (1.1) is a special case of forward finite differences of $F(x) = \binom{r-sx}{n}$ evaluated in zero $s^n = (-1)^n \Delta^n F(0)$ — it can be generalized for all x , because the coefficient of k^n remains s^n for all x

Proposition 2.1 (Generalized Knuths' Binomial identity). *For non-negative integers n , and for arbitrary integers s, r, x*

$$s^n = (-1)^n \Delta^n F(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{r - sx - sk}{n} (-1)^k$$

Because the coefficient of k^n in $\binom{r-sx-sk}{n}$ is

$$a_n = \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} \begin{bmatrix} n \\ n \end{bmatrix} [k^n]((r - sx) - sk)^n = (-1)^n \frac{s^n}{n!}$$

Because, by Binomial theorem

$$[k^n]((r - sx) - sk)^n = (-1)^n \binom{n}{0} (r - sx)^0 s^n = (-1)^n s^n$$

CONCLUSIONS

In this manuscript we have shown that the remarkable Binomial identity (1.1) given by Donald Knuth in his fundamental work entitled *Concrete Mathematics* is indeed true. In addition, we provide a generalization for identity (5.42) for all x , that is (2.1).

Figure 1. Professor Knuth at Computer Science, the Bible, and Music - 2018 Lectures.

REFERENCES

- [1] Graham, Ronald L. and Knuth, Donald E. and Patashnik, Oren. *Concrete mathematics: A foundation for computer science (second edition)*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, Inc., 1994. <https://archive.org/details/concrete-mathematics>.

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